

ECHO:

Expanding Concept and Methodology for Human Past Studies in the
Eastern Baltic Countries

Grant Agreement no 101159883

Deliverable 2.2 - Course outline on working with data

WP2 – Enriching methodological toolbox

Due date of deliverable: 31.01.2026

Dissemination level: Public

Start date of project: 01.09.2024

Duration: 36 months

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: UCPH

Author(s): Martin Petr, Alena Kushniarevich, Kristiina Tambets

Funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the “Workshop on data analysis, visualisation, and reproducibility for population genetics in R”. It provided participants with a practical introduction to R programming for data analysis in population genomics. The workshop combined brief theoretical input with extensive hands-on exercises, enabling participants to develop core skills and apply them directly to their own research projects. Overall, the workshop strengthened computational capacity within the project. The workshop aligns with the Project Objective 1: To extend methodological expertise of UTARTU through knowledge transfer from UCPH and KUL to researchers and doctoral students of UTARTU Archaeogenomics group (10 people) who will be trained in: new methods in exploring demographic processes (population movements, mixing, splits) through spatiotemporal modelling using multiple sources of information (ancient and modern genomic data, geographic, cultural, climatological data). The workshop was organised by the UCPH.

Contents

Workshop Overview and Objectives	4
Date, Location, and Format	4
Workshop Instructor.....	4
Participants	4
Workshop Programme.....	5
Workshop content and materials	5
Conclusions	6

Workshop Overview and Objectives

The workshop “Workshop on data analysis, visualisation, and reproducibility for population genetics in R” is part of the WP2 (Enriching methodological toolbox) and stays in line with the Objective 2.1: Improve UTARTU bioinformatic and statistics skills.

The workshop is focused on developing core competencies in using state-of-the-art data analysis and visualisation tools in the R ecosystem, with a special emphasis on the basics of computational reproducibility relevant to population genetics of ancient DNA. The workshop is primarily intended for master’s and PhD students, as well as early-career researchers who have not yet had much chance to expand their skills in computational aspects of population genetics research.

Date, Location, and Format

The in-person [workshop](#) took place from 13 to 17 October 2025 at the University of Tartu Library, Str. W. Struve 1, TORI room.

Workshop Instructor

The workshop is designed and led by **Martin Petr** (Assistant Professor, Globe Institute, Section for Molecular Ecology and Evolution)

Participants

Altogether, 20 people attended the workshop, of which 19 represented University of Tartu, Vilnius University and Latvian University from Eastern Baltic, one represented University of Basel (Swiss).

Workshop Programme

The workshop was designed as a highly interactive and collaborative event, providing participants with plenty of opportunities to work on their own projects and research questions throughout the programme. The aim was for each participant to be able to immediately apply the acquired knowledge and skills to their own research, regardless of their specific study focus.

The workshop **programme** consisted of five morning and five afternoon sessions. Each session began with a short introductory presentation outlining the day's topic and objectives.

Workshop content and materials

The “Workshop on data analysis, visualisation, and reproducibility for population genetics in R” is part of the course “Computational Population Genetics and Statistical Inference in R”, designed by Martin Petr. A comprehensive description of the workshop materials, as part of the whole course, is available on the instructor's personal webpage (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/>). The git repository containing the source codes for the materials of the full course is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/bodkan/simgen>.

Workshop structure

The workshop covered introduction to R, reproducible computing, *tidyverse* package, visualization with *ggplot2*, and simulations with *slendr*.

Introduction to R

- R bootcamp (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/r-bootcamp.html>)

Introduction to *tidyverse*

- Introduction to *tidyverse* (R packages *dplyr*, *readr*; fundamental application of the most important *tidyverse* functions) (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/tidy-basics.html>)
- Visualization with *ggplot2* (R package *ggplot2* intro and practice) (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/tidy-viz.html>)

Simulations with *slendr*

- Demographic models (*slendr* introduction; building demographic models using the programmable interface provided by the *slendr* R package) (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/popgen-models.html>)

- Tree-sequence statistics (compute population genetic statistics on slendr-simulated tree sequences using *slendr*'s interface to the *tskit* Python module) (<https://bodkan.net/simgen/popgen-stats.html>)

The workshop materials are structured so that each topic has a brief introduction including links for additional reading and is followed by a set of exercises with solutions provided and ends with a section with additional resources (see below a snapshot of the workshop material page). The topics are linked and easy to follow for a newcomer to the R programming environment. Alternatively, each topic can be practiced by each student on their own, and used as reference materials for their future work.

The screenshot shows the 'R bootcamp' page for 'Computational Population Genetics and Statistical Inference in R'. The page is structured as follows:

- Left Navigation Menu:**
 - Introduction
 - R language
 - R bootcamp
 - Welcome to *tidyverse*
 - Introduction to *tidyverse*
 - More *tidyverse* practice
 - Visualization with *ggplot2*
 - Reproducible computing
 - Structuring (R) projects
 - Quarto reports and slides
 - Working with spatial data
 - Plotting *tidy* spatial data
 - Simulations with *slendr*
 - Demographic models
 - Tree-sequence statistics
 - Simulation-based inference
 - N_e inference with AFS
 - Cheatsheets and handouts
 - R bootcamp
 - Introduction to *tidyverse*
 - Visualization with *ggplot2*
 - Simulations with *slendr*
 - References
 - Acknowledgements
 - Unfinished chapters
 - Exploring PCA patterns
 - Spatial PCA
 - Admixture tracts and dating
 - Natural selection
 - Algorithmic thinking
 - Command-line scripts
 - Appendices
 - Installation - *tidyverse*
 - Installation - *slendr*
 - Slides

- Main Content Area:**
- Breadcrumbs: R language > R bootcamp
- Section: **R bootcamp**
- Text: "In this first chapter, you will be exploring the fundamental, more technical aspects of the R programming language. We will focus on topics which are normally taken for granted and never explained in basic data science courses, which generally immediately jump to data manipulation and plotting."
- Text: "I strongly believe that **getting familiar with the fundamentals of R as a complete programming language from a "lower-level" perspective, although it might seem a little overwhelming at the beginning, will pay dividends over and over your scientific career.**
- Text: "**The alternative is relying on magical black box thinking, which might work when everything works smoothly... except things rarely work smoothly in anything related to computing. Bugs appear, programs crash, incorrect results are produced—only by understanding the fundamentals can you troubleshoot problems.**
- Text: "**We call this chapter a "bootcamp" on purpose - we only have a limited amount of time to go through all of these topics, and we have to rush things through a bit.** After all, the primary reason for the existence of this workshop is to make you competent researchers in computational population genomics, so the emphasis will still be on practical applications and solving concrete data science issues."
- Text: "**Still, when we get to data science work in the following chapters, you will see that many things which otherwise remain quite obscure and magical boil down to a set of very simple principles introduced here. The purpose of this chapter is to show you these fundamentals.**
- Text: "**This knowledge will make you much more confident in the results of your work, and much easier to debug issues and problems in your own projects, but also track down problems in other people's code. The later happens much more often than you might think!**
- Section: **Getting help**
- Text: "**Before we even get started, there's one thing you should remember: R (and R packages) have an absolutely stellar documentation and help system.** What's more, this documentation is standardized, has always the same format, and is accessible in the same way. The primary way of interacting with it from inside R (and RStudio) is the `?` operator. **For instance, to get help about the `hist()` function (histograms), you can type `?hist` in the R console.** This documentation has a consistent format and appears in the "Help" pane in your RStudio window."
- Text: "There are a couple of things to look for:"
 1. On the top of the documentation page, you will always see a brief description of the *arguments* of each function. This is what you'll be looking for most of the time ("How do I do specify this or that? How do I modify the behavior of the function?").
 2. On the bottom of the page are examples. These are small bits of code which often explain the behavior of some functionality in a very helpful way.
- Right Side (Table of contents):**
- Getting help
- Exercise 0: Creating an R Script and general workflow
- Exercise 1: Basic data types and variables
- Exercise 2: Vectors
- Exercise 3: Lists
- Exercise 4: Logical/boolean expressions and conditionals
- Exercise 5: Indexing into vectors and lists
- Exercise 6: Data frames
- Exercise 7: Inspecting column types
- Exercise 8: Base R plotting
- Exercise 9: Working with directories and files
- Exercise 10: Functions
- Exercise 11: Conditional expressions
- Exercise 12: Iteration and loops
- Further resources

Conclusions

The workshop provided participants with a solid introductory foundation in R programming, combining clear explanations with hands-on practice. It successfully equipped attendees with practical skills they can immediately apply to their own research projects and data analyses. The workshop established a strong basis for engagement with the upcoming workshops in the same series. The event therefore, contributed meaningfully to capacity building within the project and strengthened preparedness for more advanced training activities.